

THE LEVEL OF INTEGRATED ASSESSMENT OF ENSURING THE SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT OF INDUSTRIAL ENTERPRISES

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19840802>

Abstract. This article analyzes the theoretical and practical aspects of forming and implementing a sustainable development strategy for enterprises. The study examines the main principles of the sustainable development concept, strategic management mechanisms in enterprises, and their impact on economic efficiency based on an evolutionary approach. It also addresses the issues of ensuring the alignment of environmental, social, and economic factors in enterprise activities, as well as promoting innovation and increasing competitiveness. The research substantiates that the implementation of a sustainable development strategy enables enterprises to enhance long-term performance, ensure efficient use of resources, and maintain adaptability to changes in the external environment.

Keywords : stable development, strategic management, enterprise efficiency, innovation, competitiveness, environmental stability, economic growth.

Introduction

The development of approaches aimed at determining the level of integrated assessment of ensuring the sustainable development of industrial enterprises, as well as their analysis on the example of selected industrial enterprises, has developed significantly in recent years, but at the same time, we believe that it is also appropriate to prepare scientific works on the sustainable development of industrial enterprises located in a particular region. It is also necessary to improve approaches to the preparation of author's works, through which to develop integrated indicators.

In addition, when conducting such assessments, it is necessary to carry them out in a comprehensive manner, which will facilitate obtaining, preparing, and analyzing the final results, and will create opportunities to study and analyze all areas of the activities of industrial enterprises in the regions.

This will allow ensuring the sustainable development of industrial enterprises in the regions, improving the mechanisms for conducting economic policy, and developing scientific conclusions and recommendations based on them. Integral indicators are also important indicators in the range of macroeconomic indicators such as GDP and economic growth. The growth of integral indicators, in turn, will contribute to the separate management of the activities of industrial enterprises, the organization of production, and the achievement of a sustainable level of development. When determining the level of development of industrial enterprises, it is advisable to take into account the stabilization of elements of economic systems.

To achieve the sustainable development goals, it is necessary to address the most important issues, develop sustainable development strategies in accordance with national, international, and regional interests, through which the development of regional, national, and international strategies will serve to prepare socio-economic development strategies. Based on the recommendations of the UN, international, national, and regional development programs are being developed in the regions of the country based on three options until 2030.

According to it, the following issues are resolved:

First, to analyze government programs and strategies at the global, national, regional, and local levels to achieve sustainable development goals;

Second, consider achieving the development of global, national, regional, and local sustainable development goals;

Third, to work towards achieving sustainable development, to solve the identified tasks, and to prepare strategies to address selected problems;

Fourth, in order to achieve sustainable development, it is necessary to develop mechanisms in international regulatory frameworks at the national, regional, and local levels in order to refine strategies and programs and identify their characteristics.

The 2030 Agenda focuses on comprehensive solutions, which involves overcoming traditional barriers across sectors and implementing integrated policies with horizontal linkages at all levels - national, regional, local. To ensure an integrated policy, the following areas of horizontal communication are distinguished:

- comprehensive policy analysis: to what extent do strategies, programs and targets support national SDGs;

-coordinated institutional mechanisms: to create formally organized interactions between line ministries and departments.

Analysis of selected sustainable development monitoring indicators in the country's regions shows that further improvement of the software is currently required to implement the target indicators of the 2030 Agenda, increase the level of socio-economic development of the regions, and the standard indicators of industrial enterprise reports indicate that the statistical base of measurements is insufficient to ensure full monitoring of the assessment of the sustainable development of enterprises, as well as the lack of a "transitional" nature of the indicators, which does not allow for a gradual assessment of sustainable development.

Analysis of literature on the topic

The concept of sustainable development is based on the interdependence of economic, environmental and social factors. This approach is widely studied in international scientific literature as the "triple bottom line" principle, which involves evaluating the activities of an enterprise not only by financial results, but also by environmental and social efficiency.

In studies conducted by scientists, various systems of indicators have been proposed to assess sustainable development: environmental indicators (energy efficiency, waste volume), economic indicators (profitability, production efficiency), and social indicators (employment rate, working conditions). At the same time, the integrated assessment approach provides a comprehensive analysis by combining these indicators into a single system.

Research methodology

The following scientific methods were used in the research process:

- Integrated approach – combining different indicators into a single assessment system;

- Coefficient method - assessment of economic, environmental and social indicators in relative weights;
- Statistical analysis – quantitative study of the activities of industrial enterprises;
- Comparative method – comparing the sustainability levels of different enterprises;
- Expert assessment - determining the level of importance of indicators.

This methodology allows for a comprehensive and objective assessment of the level of sustainable development of enterprises.

Analysis and results

The conducted analyses show that the level of sustainable development in industrial enterprises is formed through the interaction of various factors. Based on the integrated assessment model, the following main areas are identified:

1. Economic stability

An enterprise's financial stability, profitability level, and production efficiency directly affect its overall sustainability index.

2. Environmental efficiency

The efficient use of resources, waste reduction, and compliance with environmental standards determine the environmental index of an enterprise.

3. Social stability

Employee working conditions, the level of social protection, and corporate social responsibility indicators represent social stability.

According to the results of the integrated assessment, enterprises with a high level of sustainability actively support innovative activities and quickly adapt to changes in the external environment.

Hierarchical structure of integrated indicators - It is appropriate to propose the following model for assessing the sustainability of industrial enterprises based on the principle of "From global goals to local results": international level (ESG and SDG): UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDG) and international ESG (Environmental, Social, and Governance) ratings. At this level, energy efficiency, "carbon footprint" and corporate governance transparency are the main criteria, national level (State Strategy): indicators from the "Uzbekistan-2030" Strategy of the Republic of Uzbekistan and state programs for industrial development. Here, the main attention is paid to the share of industry in gross regional product, the level of localization and export diversification

Table 1.1 .

Economic indicators of sustainable development of industrial enterprises in the regions¹

No.	Sustainable development indicators	Formula for calculation	
Production unit P $P_{1iqt} = (\alpha_1 * F_{1iqt} + \alpha_2 * F_{2iqt})$			
1	Manufacturing Labor Index F_{1iqt}	The productivity of labor in the enterprise is higher than that of the leading competitor	

¹Author's development

		ratio of this indicator	
2	Composition of fixed assets F_{2iqt}	ratio of the value of newly introduced fixed assets to the total value of fixed assets at the end of the reporting period	
Marketing block P $P_{2iqt} = (\alpha_3 * F_{3iqt} + \alpha_4 * F_{4iqt})$			
1	Trade volume index F_{3iqt}	Ratio of sales volume in the reporting period and the previous period	
2	Modified market share F_{4iqt}	The volume of sales of the main product of the industrial enterprise, relative to the leading competitor	
Operation block P $P_{3iqt} = (\alpha_5 * F_{5iqt} + \alpha_6 * F_{6iqt})$			
1	Sales profitability F_{5iqt}	The relationship between income and expenditure	
2	Total revenue minus personnel expenses F_{6iqt}	General wage payment for gainful employment	
Investment block P $P_{4iqt} = (\alpha_7 * F_{7iqt})$			
1	Investment activity F_{7iqt}	The amount of investment expenses as a percentage of total income	
Innovation block P $P_{5iqt} = (\alpha_8 * F_{8iqt} + \alpha_9 * F_{9iqt})$			
1	Innovation potential F_{8iqt}	The volume of spending on innovative developments in total revenues	
2	Innovative product F_{9iqt}	The relationship between the sales of innovative products and services in the structure of the enterprise's total	

		revenues and the volume of total revenue	
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In Figure 1.1, the aim was to select and analyze only economic indicators to ensure the stabilization of the activities of industrial enterprises in the regions, thereby ensuring the sustainable development of industrial enterprises in the region.

The structural structure of the system of economic indicators serving the sustainable development of industrial enterprises in the regions consists of production, marketing, operations, investment, and innovation blocks. In addition, it is possible to include information technologies and artificial intelligence in these indicators. We believe that these indicators will serve to ensure the sustainable development of the activities of industrial enterprises and will help in finding ways to effectively use raw material supply and financial issues.

In addition, there are opportunities for the widespread use of information technologies and artificial intelligence technologies in monitoring the sales of industrial enterprises' products or organizing their sales in the future. In addition, based on the widespread use of neural networks in practice, industrial enterprises can be clustered, and it is advisable to use them in regulating the management processes of operating industrial enterprises, in identification work, for this reason, their widespread use is necessary.

Table 1.2.

Namangan region stable industry integrated development assessment degrees

No.	Index value	Sustainability level	explanation
1	0.80-1.00	High	Industry enterprises stable growing is going
2	0.60-0.79	Stable	Development good , but some on the networks disadvantages there is
3	0.40-0.59	Medium	In development stagnation divine
4	0.20-0.39	Low	Seriously economic or social problems there is
5	0.00-0.19	Crisis	Industry enterprises stability whole lost

Namangan in the province industry stable develop according to analytical information your dissertation practical part for basis to be service does . Namangan province Uzbekistan industrialized from the regions one to be , to be stable development to oneself typical network composition and resource to the possibilities relies on .

amangan province industry stability many in terms of textile and sewing-knitting to the network related

Leader Industries : Textiles (industry) size about 45-50% of the total), food , leather and footwear and construction materials working release

Regional Distribution : Industry of capacity main part of Namangan city , Turakurgan (electricity) energy on account of) and Chust to the districts right is coming .

Strategic Objects : Turakurgan TPP region industry energetic stability provider main download link . Industry of enterprises stability their external in the market instead of related . In Namangan region working issued industry products export dynamics as follows analysis is done :

Export Direction : Export in the composition ready clothes and fruits and vegetables again work products high to share has .

Stable development basis this is the main to capital included Foreign investments Investments : Latest in years Germany , Turkey and China investments on account of textile clusters and pharmaceuticals factories to work Technological level : " Industry 4.0" elements current to grow through energy spending reduce (energy efficiency) stable development ecological block organization is doing

Conclusion

In order to develop all countries in the world economy, it is necessary to first study the current situation and economy in their regions, create opportunities for the regions to use their economic and social potential, and ensure the stability of the activities of industrial enterprises in them by rapidly developing the regions of each country. In this regard, ways of sustainable development of the activities of industrial enterprises in the regions of the Republic of Uzbekistan have been developed, proposals for corresponding strategies have been formulated, while ensuring the rapid high rates of development of the national economy directly involve ensuring the rapid development of the economies of the regions, and accelerating the sustainable development of the activities of industrial enterprises in the regions, in turn, involves developing a number of proposals and recommendations based on scientific conclusions.

1. Based on the sustainable development indicators developed by the United Nations, "Indicators for the Achievement of Sustainable Development Goals" have been developed to ensure the sustainability of the activities of industrial enterprises in the regions of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

2. Based on the above research, indicators for achieving sustainable development goals were grouped into four major groups: "ecological", "economic", "social", and "institutional". Industrial enterprises in the regions should pay attention to these groups of indicators in their activities, otherwise, if an imbalance occurs in any of these groups, it will affect the socio-economic development of not just one industrial enterprise in the region, but the entire region.

3. To ensure the sustainability of the activities of industrial enterprises in the regions, a separate "indicators for achieving sustainable development goals for industrial enterprises" were developed, according to which these indicators were divided into four large groups consisting of 10 indicators based on the UN guidelines and were proposed to be evaluated on a five-point system, and then "criteria for indicators for sustainable development of industrial enterprises" were developed,

4. By monitoring sustainable development indicators, various options are developed, which are used to process the set of indicators, identify and systematize problems in the activities of industrial enterprises, thereby developing the composition of these options.

References used:

1. Investment in Artificial Intelligence Solutions Will Accelerate as Businesses Seek Insights, Efficiency, and Innovation, According to a New IDC Spending Guide // International Data Corporation, 2021. — URL: [idc.com/getdoc.jsp?containerId=prUS48191221](https://www.idc.com/getdoc.jsp?containerId=prUS48191221).
2. Shell, C3 AI, Baker Hughes, and Microsoft Launch the Open AI Energy Initiative, an Ecosystem of AI Solutions to Help Transform the Energy Industry // C3.ai [site], 2021. — URL: [c3.ai/shell-c3-ai-baker-hughes-and-microsoft-launch-the-open-ai-energy-initiative-an-ecosystem-of-ai-solutions-to-help-transform-the-energy-industry](https://www.c3.ai/shell-c3-ai-baker-hughes-and-microsoft-launch-the-open-ai-energy-initiative-an-ecosystem-of-ai-solutions-to-help-transform-the-energy-industry).
3. Notes from the AI frontier: Insights from hundreds of use cases / M. Chui, J. Manyika, M. Miremadi [et al.] // McKinsey [site], 2018. — URL: [mckinsey.com/featured-insights/artificial-intelligence/notes-from-the-ai-frontier-applications-and-value-of-deep-learning](https://www.mckinsey.com/featured-insights/artificial-intelligence/notes-from-the-ai-frontier-applications-and-value-of-deep-learning).
4. Iz styupleniya Sanjiva Shrivastava na seminare " A.I. Driven Design " Approach " // YouTube channel Machine
5. Learning Center at Georgia Tech [site], 2020. — URL: [youtube.com/watch?v=eitWsEM2ljk](https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=eitWsEM2ljk).
6. Wunner F. How AI-driven generative design disrupts traditional value chains / F. Wunner, T. Krüger, B. Gierse // Accenture [site], 2020. — URL: [accenture.com/us-en/blogs/industry-digitization/how-ai-driven-generative-design-disrupts-traditional-value-chains](https://www.accenture.com/us-en/blogs/industry-digitization/how-ai-driven-generative-design-disrupts-traditional-value-chains).
7. Stiglitz, J.E., Sen, A., and J.-P. Fitoussi (2009). Report by the Commission on the Measurement of Economic Performance and Social Progress.
8. Sala, S.; Farioli, F.; Zamagni, A. Progress in sustainability science: Lessons learned from current methodologies for sustainability assessment: Part 1. *Int. J. Life Cycle Assess.* 2012, 18, 1653-1672. [Google Scholar] [CrossRef]
1. Nuri Cihat Onat, Murat Kucukvar, Anthony Halog, Scott Cloutier. Systems Thinking for Life Cycle Sustainability Assessment: A Review of Recent Developments, Applications, and Future Perspectives *Sustainability* 2017,9(5), 706; doi :10.3390/su9050706
2. ХОЛМИРЗАЕВ, У., & ХАКИМОВА, Г. ЭКОНОМИКА И МЕНЕДЖМЕНТ: НОВЫЕ ВЫЗОВЫ И ВОЗМОЖНОСТИ. Донской государственный технический университет КОНФЕРЕНЦИЯ: ЭКОНОМИКА И МЕНЕДЖМЕНТ: НОВЫЕ ВЫЗОВЫ И ВОЗМОЖНОСТИ Ростов-на-Дону, 22 февраля 2024 года Организаторы: Донской государственный технический университет.
3. Холмирзаев, У. А., & Хакимова, Г. А. (2024). РАЗВИТИЕ АГРАРНОГО СЕКТОРА ЭКОНОМИКИ РЕГИОНА НА ОСНОВЕ ИННОВАЦИЙ. *Экономика и менеджмент: новые вызовы и возможности*, 731.
4. Abdulazizovich, X. U. B. (2025). DAVLAT-XUSUSIY SHERIKLIK MODELLARI, SHAKLLARI VA MEXANIZMLARI TASNIFI. *Raqamli iqtisodiyot (Цифровая экономика)*, (13. I), 2516-2532.
5. Abdulazizovich, X. U. (2025). BILIMLAR IQTISODIYOTINI SHAKLLANTIRISH SHAROITIDA TA'LIM SOHASINING RIVOJLANISH TENDENSIYALARI. *Marketing Jurnal*, (2).
6. Abdulazizovich, X. U. (2025). O'ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASI HUDUDLARIDA BILIM IQTISODIYOTINING RIVOJLANISH DARAJASINI BAHOLASH UCHUN USLUBIY YORDAMNI SHAKLLANTIRISH. *Marketing Jurnal*, (3).
7. Kholmiraev, U. A. (2025). Economy of knowledge in the evolution of neoclassical and post-schumpeterian models of economic growth. *IIm, tadqiqot va taraqqiyot/Наука, исследования и развитие*, 3(11), 70-77.

- 8.Xolmirzayev, U. B., & Ubaydullayev, T. (2026). NOTIJORAT TASHKILOTLAR FAOLIYATIDA AUDITORLIK TEKSHIRUVI VA AUDITORLIK HISOBOTLARINING O 'ZIGA XOSLIGI. *Muhandislik va iqtisodiyot*, 4(3).
- 9.Abdulazizovich, X. U. B., & Yoqubjon o'g'li, B. Q. (2026). BUDJET TASHKILOTLARI XARAJATLARINI MOLIYALASHTIRISH SAMARADORLIGI VA BUDJETDAN TASHQARI MABLAG 'LARNING IQTISODIY AHAMIYATI. *FARS International Journal of Education, Social Science & Humanities.*, 14(3), 40-49.
- 10.Abdulazizovich, X. U. B., & Murodillayevich, N. J. (2026). O 'ZBEKISTONDA MAHALLIY BUDJET DAROMADLARI SHAKLLANISHINING AMALDAGI HOLATI TAHLILI. *American Journal of Business Management*, 4(3), 43-51.
- 11.Abdulazizovich, K. U. (2026). The superiority of cooperation over competition in the development process: theoretical and practical approaches. *American Journal of Social Science*, 4(3), 38-47.
- 12.Xolmirzayev, U. A., & Xakimova, G. A. (2023). Xo 'jalik yurituvchi subyektlarda debitor qarzlarning aylanishi tahliliga zamonaviy yondashuvlar.
- 13.Xolmirzayev, U. A. (2023). Debitor qarzlarni aylanishi tahlilini takomillashtirish masalalari.[Ilmiy maqola].
- 14.Xolmirzayev, U. B., & Normatov, J. (2026). MAHALLIY BUDJETLARNI BOSHQARISHDA RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALAR VA OCHIQLIKNI KUCHAYTIRISH. *MUHANDISLIK VA IQTISODIYOT*, 4(2).
- 15.Madrimov, A., Ulug'Muradova, N., Ravshanov, A., Kholmirzaev, U., Egamberdiyeva, I., & Nortoeva, U. (2025, April). Predicting Tourist Spending Behavior Using Bayesian Networks. In *2025 International Conference on Computational Innovations and Engineering Sustainability (ICCIES)* (pp. 1-5). IEEE.
- 16.Sobirjon O'g'li, J. E., & Abdulazizovich, X. U. B. (2019). Profits of housekeeping and its development. *Asian Journal of Multidimensional Research (AJMR)*, 8(4), 419-423.
- 17.ХОЛМИРЗАЕВ, У., & КАМОЛДИНОВ, О. ЭКОНОМИКА И СОЦИУМ. *ЭКОНОМИКА*, 625-627.
- 18.Batirova, R., & Xolmirzayev, U. B. *Ulgurji Savdo Qoidalari Va Chakana Savdodan Farqli Tomonlari. Green Economy and Development*, 3(9), 666890.
- 19.Xolmirzayev, U. B., & Ubaydullayev, T. O 'zbekiston Respublikasida Davlat-xususiy Sheriklik Sohasida Me'yoriy-huquqiy Bazani Ishlab Chiqish. *Green Economy and Development*, 3(10), 667114.

